

Automatic Volume Balancing for Online Refueling in Molten Salt Reactor Simulations with SCALE

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ABSTRACT

This work introduces recently implemented capabilities in the SCALE code system's TRITON reactor physics sequence that improve molten salt reactor (MSR) modeling: (1) a volume balancing option, which automatically balances the volumes of the fed material with a corresponding material removal to maintain fixed mixture volumes in the neutron transport model and accurate densities, and (2) *continuous feed from mixtures*, which enables users to define material feed streams directly from salt mixture definitions rather than individual nuclides.

The new capabilities were demonstrated via SCALE/TRITON simulations of two representative MSR concepts. Simulations of the 180 MW_{th} molten chloride fast reactor—a system with a fixed fuel salt volume in the reactor core—applied continuous refueling with fresh fuel salt. The results confirm approximately constant reactivity when the new volume balancing capability is used. Additionally, excellent agreement with a manual feed-and-drain method for volume balancing further verified the new implementation. Simulations of the 400 MW_{th} EIRENE reactor, an integral MSR in which the salt volume may grow over time within the reactor core, demonstrated the capability to represent growing salt volume within the TRITON depletion calculation. Compared with reference solutions, the results show consistent trends in reactivity and isotopic evolution, confirming that these new user-friendly capabilities provide accurate, physically consistent approaches for modeling MSRs in SCALE.

Keywords: molten salt reactor (MSR), depletion, online refueling, SCALE, TRITON

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten salt reactors (MSRs) have attracted renewed interest as promising advanced reactor concepts that offer high fuel utilization, flexible fuel cycles, and inherent safety characteristics. A distinguishing feature of MSRs is the use of liquid fuel salt, which enables online refueling and removal of fission products, in contrast to solid-fueled reactors, in which the core composition evolves only through depletion. This dynamic behavior poses a modeling challenge for simulation tools, particularly for depletion calculations, because the fuel composition evolves not only through nuclear transmutation processes (fission, absorption, and decay) but also through feed and removal operations.

To capture and simulate these dynamic depletion behaviors, Monte Carlo-based reactor physics simulation tools, including SCALE [1], OpenMC [2], and Serpent [3], have extended their depletion capabilities and enabled continuous material feed and fractional removal of nuclides such as fission products. However, several modeling challenges remain for modeling all MSR designs that are currently

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proposed. One important issue is the handling of a continuously increasing fuel salt volume due to ongoing feed operations. For the discussion of this issue, we distinguish between two MSR designs: (1) loop systems, in which the fuel salt flows through a loop before reentering the reactor core (e.g., molten salt breeder reactor [MSBR] [4]), and (2) integral systems, in which all fuel salt is contained in the reactor core at all times (e.g., integral molten salt reactor [IMSR] [5]). In loop systems, the fuel salt volume in the core is constant, and the addition of fuel salt volume during operation results in an increase in the fuel salt volume in the loop, likely by a rising level in a specific area of the loop. In integral systems, the fuel salt level may rise during operation due to the continuous fuel salt feed. In a neutron transport model, specific materials are assigned to areas in a fixed geometry. Without any balancing mechanisms, the application of a material feed causes the total mass and density of the fuel salt to increase without bound, potentially leading to unphysical conditions and inaccurate simulation results.

Previous work [4] addressed this challenge in loop systems by including a material removal in the simulation, in which a portion of the fuel salt was continuously removed according to the fuel salt feed rate to keep the fuel salt volume approximately constant. This *feed-and-drain* approach stabilizes the core volume in simulations with continuous feed. A drawback of this method, however, is that it requires the user to manually specify the fuel salt removal rate, which cannot be determined accurately in advance because it depends on the time-dependent solution of the system—information that is not available a priori.

For integral MSR systems, Moss et al. [6] employed Python scripting to run and chain separate Serpent or SCALE calculations for each time step. In this approach, the critical fuel salt feed rate and the corresponding volume increase are computed and then propagated to the subsequent depletion step. Volume changes are captured by updating the simulation geometry at each depletion step when the feed is added. Although effective, the scripting approach is not user-friendly: It requires significant user effort, is prone to error, and introduces an additional dependency on external scripts, making it impractical as a long-term solution.

In this work, an automatic volume balancing capability for MSR simulations was implemented in SCALE 7.0 beta version under development, fully integrated within all TRITON sequences. This capability calculates the volume that is added to a mixture through a specified material feed and then removes an equivalent volume of the final mixture to ensure mixture volume conservation. Depending on the reactor design, the removed salt can either be transferred to another region within the core or extracted from the system, simulating transfer to an external storage tank. Additionally, as part of this implementation, user convenience was improved by enabling material feed directly from specific mixtures (e.g., a fresh fuel salt mixture) instead of having to specify individual nuclides each with a different feed rate.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews current MSR modeling capabilities in SCALE, Section 3 describes the new extensions (the new volume balancing capability and the continuous feed from mixtures), Section 4 demonstrates applications, and Section 5 provides conclusions.

2. CURRENT MSR CAPABILITIES IN SCALE

SCALE [1] provides several capabilities for modeling MSRs [7] and is being continuously developed to enable more realistic and accurate analyses of such systems. Key capabilities for MSR analysis are implemented in SCALE's general reactor physics sequence, TRITON. TRITON performs depletion calculations by coupling a neutron transport solver (one of SCALE's 1D, 2D, or 3D neutron transport kernels, for computing the neutron flux and reaction rates) with the ORIGEN depletion and decay solver (for updating the material composition). The governing depletion equation for nuclide i is

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = \sum_{j=1}^n l_{ij} \lambda_j N_j + \phi \sum_{k=1}^n f_{ik} \sigma_k N_k - (\lambda_i + \phi \sigma_i) N_i ; \quad (1)$$

where:

- N_i : amount of nuclide i (atoms),
- λ_j : decay constant of nuclide j (1/s),
- l_{ij} : fractional yield of nuclide i from decay of nuclide j ,
- ϕ : angle- and energy-integrated neutron flux (n/cm²/s),
- σ_k : spectrum-averaged microscopic cross section for nuclide k (barn),
- f_{ik} : fraction of neutron-induced reactions on nuclide k that produce nuclide i .

TRITON supports several model updates throughout the depletion calculation. In addition to the material updates, such as temperature changes, two types of material flow were implemented specifically for MSR analysis:

- **Fractional Removal Flow**

This capability allows the user to remove a specified fraction of selected nuclides from a mixture in the neutron transport model at designated depletion steps by specifying a removal constant in unit [1/s]. It is typically applied to simulate the continuous extraction of fission products from the fuel salt—for example, xenon and krypton through the off-gas system. Multiple removal streams can be defined within a single depletion calculation. Removed nuclides are directed to another mixture, typically a mixture *outside* the neutron transport model for which only nuclide decay is considered (labeled *decay-only* mixture). This decay-only mixture may, for example, represent a removal system such as the off-gas system or a fuel salt dump tank for storage and tracking. For this removal mechanism, the depletion equation is modified by adding a fractional removal term $\lambda_{i,\text{rem}}N_i$, with $\lambda_{i,\text{rem}}$ as the user-specified fractional removal constant for nuclide i .

- **Continuous Feed Flow**

This capability allows the user to specify a constant mass flow rate in units [g/s, kg/s, moles/s] of selected nuclides into a target mixture during depletion. The nuclides are added continuously over the depletion step. The feed is represented in the depletion equation as a constant source term. Although this approach has proven to be useful and effective in previous modeling efforts, it has two notable limitations:

1. The continuous increase of the target mixture mass can lead to unrealistic density growth if the target mixture volume is constant.
2. Feed is restricted to **nuclide-only specifications**, requiring the user to define individual feed rates for each nuclide. This can be cumbersome and error-prone, especially for complex fuel salt compositions.

3. EXTENSIONS TO SCALE CAPABILITIES FOR MSR MODELING

To address the limitations of the existing MSR depletion capabilities and to enable more realistic modeling of such systems, TRITON's material flow capabilities have been extended to include (1) a volume conservation option and (2) continuous feed from mixture definitions. These enhancements simplify user input and extend the range of MSR scenarios that can be modeled directly in SCALE without reliance on external scripts.

3.1. Volume balancing Option

As mentioned earlier, a key challenge in modeling MSR refueling is maintaining physical salt densities under continuous material feed. Without volume balancing, the total mass of the receiving mixture increases indefinitely, leading to unphysically high densities and unphysical results.

To address this challenge, a new option for volume balancing was introduced into TRITON's continuous feed capability. When enabled, TRITON automatically removes a portion of the target mixture equivalent to the incoming material feed volume, thereby ensuring a constant target mixture volume

and physical mass density.

Internally, TRITON generates a fractional removal block (see Section 2) in which all nuclides present in the fuel mixture—including those that are built up during depletion—are removed at rates computed to exactly balance the incoming feed.

For a specific point in time, let the target mixture have density ρ_{target} , receiving feed at a rate of \dot{m}_{feed} (g/s) from a source mixture with density ρ_{source} . To conserve the target mixture volume, the following total mass removal rate is applied to the target mixture:

$$\dot{m}_{\text{removal}} = \dot{m}_{\text{feed}} \times \frac{\rho_{\text{target}}(t)}{\rho_{\text{source}}} \quad (2)$$

Note that the mass density of the target mixture changes with time because of depletion and changes in the nuclide masses due to both production and loss processes. This means that the total removal rate also changes with time, even if the feed rate itself is kept fixed, because it depends on the current density of the target mixture. For an individual nuclide i with weight fraction w_i^m in the target mixture, the corresponding removal rate is

$$\dot{m}_{\text{removal},i} = w_i^m \times \dot{m}_{\text{feed}} \times \frac{\rho_{\text{target}}(t)}{\rho_{\text{source}}} \quad (3)$$

Putting everything together, the depletion equation with continuous feed and the volume balancing option becomes

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = \underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^n l_{ij}\lambda_j N_j + \phi \sum_{k=1}^n f_{ik}\sigma_k N_k - (\lambda_i + \phi\sigma_i)N_i}_{\text{original physics}} + \underbrace{c_i w_i^f \dot{m}_{\text{feed}}}_{\text{continuous feed}} - \underbrace{\left(\frac{\dot{m}_{\text{feed}}}{\rho_{\text{source}} V}\right) N_i(t)}_{\text{new:removal term for volume balancing}} \quad ; \quad (4)$$

where c_i is the mass-to-atom conversion factor, w_i^f is the weight fraction of the nuclide i in the source mixture, and V is the volume of the target mixture.

When the volume balancing option is used in TRITON, an additional mixture must be defined to receive the mass removed from the target mixture. Depending on the application, this mixture can be defined either as a decay-only mixture for tracking removed material or as a depletable mixture that exists in the neutron transport model.

For user convenience, TRITON reports the total mass removal rate, \dot{m}_{removal} , at each depletion step. In addition, warning statements are issued if the mixture density changes by more than 1%, and the calculation is automatically terminated if the density exceeds 20 g/cm³, which would indicate an unphysical feed rate and therefore an unphysical mixture mass.

3.2. Continuous Feed from Mixtures

The continuous feed feature in TRITON has been extended to allow the feed source to be a mixture, in addition to the existing option of specifying individual nuclides. The composition of a source mixture must be defined in the same way as all other mixtures used in the model. For example, this allows users to define a fresh fuel salt composition that serves for online refueling during operation and to apply a single feed rate to this one source mixture. Previously, users had to define a list of nuclides with corresponding individual feed rates, which can be difficult to verify for correctness.

During depletion, TRITON computes the feed rate of each nuclide based on its weight fraction in the source mixture and the total feed rate specified for that mixture. This enhancement reduces user effort and errors, and it more closely reflects practical MSR operation, in which feed streams are prepared from bulk mixtures.

4. APPLICATIONS

To demonstrate TRITON's new capabilities, two cases for two distinct MSR designs are considered:

- **Case 1:** Modeling continuous feed-and-drain balance in a fixed-volume system (i.e., the molten chloride fast reactor [MCFR]). This case represents a closed-loop system in which the fuel salt volume in the core is constant.
- **Case 2:** Modeling fuel salt volume growth during refueling (EIRENE). This case represents integral systems in which fuel salt is allowed to grow in the core.

The following subsections describe the application setup and the results for each case. The first case is an MCFR derived from prior work [8]. The second is the EIRENE design developed at the University of Tennessee, Knoxville [6].

4.1. MCFR: Fixed-Volume System with Feed-and-Drain Balance

Figure 1 shows the simplified core of the 180 MW_{th} MCFR. The core includes a pool of fuel salt, a surrounding MgO reflector, and an Inconel vessel. The active region is 3 m in diameter and 2.76 m in height. The reflector is 48 cm thick and is enclosed by a 1 cm Inconel shell. The initial fuel salt is NaCl–UCl with a 66.7–33.3 mol % ratio, and the uranium is enriched to 13.30 wt % ²³⁵U. The feed salt uses the same molar composition, but the enrichment is increased to as much as 19.75 wt % ²³⁵U. One year of operation was modeled. During depletion, xenon and krypton were removed continuously at a removal rate of 1/30 s⁻¹. A set of noble metal fission products (Zn, Ga, Ge, As, Se, Zr, Nb, Mo, Tc, Ru, Rh, Pd, Ag, Cd, In, Sn, Sb, and Te) were also removed at a removal rate of 1/3600 s⁻¹. Makeup fuel was injected from day 91 through day 365. Before day 90, the initial excess reactivity was sufficient to maintain criticality without makeup feed. The initial enrichment was adjusted to yield ~ 500 pcm of excess reactivity to compensate for reactivity loss due to delayed neutron advection. The determined multiplication factor and isotopic buildup for key nuclides (Figure 2), as determined with TRITON and the new capabilities, were compared against a manual feed-and-drain approach using both SCALE/TRITON and Serpent. The results show good agreement, providing consistent trends in reactivity and isotopic evolution. As is evident in Figure 2, the evolution of isotopic inventories for ¹³⁵Xe, ²³⁵U, ²³⁸U, and ²³⁹Pu coincides among the 3 codes/methods.

Figure 1. SCALE model of 180 MW_{th} MCFR [8].

4.2. EIRENE: Modeling Fuel Salt Volume Growth

The EIRENE design was chosen to demonstrate the growth of the fuel salt volume within the transport model. It is a 400 MW_{th} reactor. As makeup fuel salt is added during operation, the fuel salt expands into the helium plenum at the top of the core, and therefore the salt volume increases with time. The fuel is LiF–BeF₂–UF₄ with a molar composition of 63.33%, 31.67%, and 5%. In this study, the initial salt contains uranium enriched to 2.69 wt % ²³⁵U, and the makeup salt is enriched to 5 wt % ²³⁵U.

Figure 2. Evolution of the effective multiplication factor (left) and selected isotopics (right) with different simulation approaches to accommodate makeup fuel feed in the MCFR.

To establish a reference solution, a Python-scripted workflow was used to simulate the fuel salt volume growth during operation. Depletion was simulated for 399 days, with depletion steps of 7 days. When the excess reactivity fell below 200 pcm, a search was performed for the makeup fuel addition that restored the excess reactivity to about 400 pcm. Each time makeup fuel salt was added, the TRITON neutron transport model was updated so that the fuel salt volume in the top region increased by the corresponding amount. The salt composition used by TRITON was updated by blending the makeup salt with the irradiated salt using ORIGEN. This reference procedure yielded a feed rate of 0.5745 g/s and is labeled EIRENE Case 0. Note that this simulation used many individual, chained TRITON depletion calculations in which mixture compositions and the neutron transport model were updated in the TRITON input for each simulated step. Figure 3 shows the core configuration at beginning of life (BOL) and end of life (EOL), illustrating the associated volume increase.

Informed by the reference feed rate and schedule, three additional cases were evaluated to assess TRITON's new capabilities:

1. **Case 1: Salt removed from system.** This case applied the manual feed-and-drain approach without the volume balancing capability.
2. **Case 2: Salt removed from core to decay-only tank.** The volume balancing capability is enabled. The balance mixture that received the removed fuel salt was defined as a decay-only mixture (i.e., a mixture outside the neutron transport model). This case did not simulate growing salt volume in the core. In other words, the volume of fuel salt in the core is held constant. However, the volume balancing capability caused the fuel salt composition in the core to be representative.
3. **Case 3: Salt transferred from core to plenum.** The volume balancing capability is enabled. In contrast to Case 2, the balance mixture that received the removed fuel salt was placed in the helium plenum region above the main core region and thus experienced irradiation from the low neutron flux in that region. In this setting, the additions of a certain fuel salt volume for refueling caused a corresponding transfer of salt from the main core region to the region above, approximating a volume growth of salt in the reactor. Because the total mass in this "balance" region increases at each time step when feed is applied, the mixture density correspondingly increases. This is an approximation and is acceptable because the region is neutronically unimportant and is depleted separately from the core fuel salt. Additionally, no mixing between the two mixtures is modeled. Ideally, the fuel-salt compositions in both regions should remain similar at all times, given the short circulation time in the loop. This consideration is planned in future SCALE/TRITON code development. Nevertheless, this treatment represents the most physically realistic configuration among the three cases.

Figure 3. SCALE model of the EIRENE 400 MW_{th} core at BOL (left) and EOL (right), generated by the Python-scripted workflow (Case 0).

Figure 4. Evolution of the effective multiplication factor (left) and selected isotopics (right) with different simulation approaches to accommodate makeup fuel feed in EIRENE.

Note that the same feed rate of 0.5745 g/s was used for cases 1-3 at the same time steps where feed is applied in the reference case. Figure 4 compares the multiplication factor and the isotopic buildup of key nuclides for all EIRENE cases against the reference solution. The results show close agreement, with consistent trends in reactivity and isotopic evolution. The increase in the multiplication factor corresponds to the scheduled feed additions where the introduction of fresh salt temporarily boosts reactivity. The reactivity gradually decreased due to depletion and fission-product buildup. The multiplication factor is slightly lower than the reference at later times, but inventories of important nuclides, including ²³⁵U and ²³⁹Pu, agree well with the reference. Note that the curves of ²³⁹Pu for cases 1–3 coincide. These results indicate that the new volume balancing capability can be used to approximate MSR systems with growing fuel salt levels in the core.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Two new capabilities have been implemented in the SCALE/TRITON sequence to enhance the modeling of MSRs: (1) a volume balancing option and (2) continuous feed from mixtures. These extensions ensure that the density of the target mixture (fuel salt in the MSR core) receiving material feed (makeup fuel salt) remains physical even with high feed rates. Additionally, these extensions allow modeling of a wider range of MSR designs, including those with fixed core volumes or those with growing salt volume. They also simplify input preparation by allowing feed streams to be defined in terms of salt mixtures rather than individual nuclides.

The new features were demonstrated using two representative MSR concepts. In the MCFR case, the new approach reproduced the results of the established feed-and-drain methodology, demonstrating equivalent reactivity and isotopic evolution while eliminating the need for manual removal rate specification.

In the EIRENE case, where the fuel salt volume is allowed to grow in the core, the volume balancing capability provided a good approximation for k_{eff} and the nuclide densities, showing excellent agreement with a Python-scripted reference workflow.

Overall, these results confirm that the new SCALE capabilities provide a robust, user-friendly framework for modeling online refueling and salt volume changes in MSRs. Future enhancements planned for SCALE/TRITON include automated criticality search capabilities and the implementation of a precursor drift model.

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